

The Context of Culture-Oriented Literary Aesthetics in Collegiate English Studies

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Abstract

The immense significance of English in the world today has informed the study of the language at the collegiate level as an area of interest. The essence of studying the language at the university level is to enhance the proficiency of speakers of this international language. The contents of English courses in most of the nonnative universities in Africa, however, tend to hamper the realisation of the core objective of the language programme. Emphasis has often been placed on structural elements such as parts of speech, morphological processes, phrases, clauses, or types of sentence. This practice has its limitations, which is the training of speakers who are only able to define linguistic structural items. Such speakers however, would err in actual language use in culture-oriented social situations. Such emphasises the extension of structural grammar to the aesthetic context, which signifies that language efficiency, the domain of aesthetics, needs be underscored in English studies at the collegiate level. A disregard for the aesthetic naturally eventuates in a wide gulf in training the users of the English language at the global level, and this bars international intelligibility. The gap created can be filled only by extending structural discourses to the aesthetic context or functional literariness. This is in line with the phenomenon of socio-cultural realities characteristically influencing language use. Moreover, this informs an aesthetic modification in the course contents for English studies at the collegiate in nonnative universities.

Key words: English, Aesthetics, Structure, Literariness, Culture

Introduction

The study of English at the non-native universities, particularly in Africa, hinges significantly on the theoretical perspective on syntactic elements such as inflection, conjugation, voice, mood, inversion, apposition, phrase, clause, as well as sentence typology. To this end, the fulfillment of structural principles especially as Noam Chomsky postulates in Transformational Generative Grammar or Michael Halliday stipulates in Systemic Grammar is taken for English. This is in utter disdain for the all-important, culture-oriented language aesthetics. A huge vacuum, therefore, is created in the process of training the users of the language in the global space. This vacuum, however, is filled by extending structural discourses to the aesthetic context (as the socio-cultural realities dictate) in collegiate course contents, as explained further in this discourse.

From Structure to Aesthetics

Syntax (structure) and aesthetics are two sub-fields of English studies. These two areas of interest are markedly distinct from each other in opposite phases. Syntax or structure is the domain of examining the constituents of words and sentences with emphasis on how these work together to form a meaningful whole. We can postulate that morphological processes such as affixation and syntactic investigation constitute the structure in English. Specifically, the inflection of the stem with prefixes and suffixes, and such conceptual terms as concord, inversion, antecedent, and clause structure, as well as sentence typology constitute structure in English. On the contrary, aesthetics in language is the *beauty* of language. The *beauty* being referred to in this definition is effectiveness and efficiency of language to the hearer. The effect of the effectiveness and efficiency is peculiarly marked by and manifests in smiles, nods, giggles, screams by the hearer – one at a time, a combination of a number of these at a time, or all, at a time. Moreover, these cues or hearer's reactions/responses signal and confirm the comprehension of the speaker's utterance(s). In other words, language is functioning through its aesthetics. Therefore, there is a link between functionality of language and aesthetics, and this is achieved by circumventing or through the extension of, structure/syntax to the aesthetic realm in the pedagogical process for the language/course at the collegiate level.

Syntax is the process through which words, phrases, and clauses combine to form a sentence. Radford (2004) calls it syntactic structure which he describes as how words are combined together to form phrases and sentences. Most non-native scholars rather than it being seen as a grammar of English have taken the knowledge of this for the grammar of English. Grammar may be seen as the study of how people use a language, and the

emphasis on correctness of expressions when certain given rules are followed (Sinclair 2010:6). From the foregoing, it is noted that syntax is not concerned with how language is used. It de-emphasises correctness of expressions, not in terms of observing concord and its rules especially nominal and verbal number, but disdaining the utilitarian essence of correctness in society.

Today, collegiate English grammar course contents in most non-native universities glorify syntactic grammar (the Chomsky's path) while minimal (if any, at all) attention is given to aesthetic (functional) context. It is inconsistent with the realities in intelligibility of language use that at the collegiate level, grammar is still erroneously wholly perceived to be morphology, syntax, phonology, semantics, or a combination of all. Rather, these should have been made to constitute a minimal content (say 20/80 percent ratio) of collegiate grammar of English. Such a misconception has occasioned a theoretical perspective to pedagogical investigation of the English language in the specified category of universities. As a result of this, attention has been paid to definitions of parts of speech and the numbers of them there are; including whether the article (definite article 'the') is a part of speech or not. Emphasis is laid on the types of the parts of speech, for instance, the abstract noun, predicate adjective, reciprocal pronouns and so on. It is observed today that students at the university level are essentially taught types of sentence – both in terms of its structure and functions. Being taught characteristically as grammar (of the English language) in the higher institutions these days are phrases, clauses, sentences (similarities and differences emphasised), clause structure, active voice, etymological investigation of words, diachronic assessment of the English language, socio-linguistic typology, allophone, phoneme, as well as minimal pairs. All these are theoretical, and they, on their own, do not transmit meanings and information to the hearer. This, however, contravenes the observation that '...language should have communication in view' (Akwanya 2005: 8). The crux of this assertion is that the learning of a language, including the use of it should be structured purposively, such that thoughts and information should be transmitted to the listener. However, this primary objective is definitely unattainable following the asymmetry of how the English language is taught/studied at the collegiate level in most non-native universities. This is because the course contents as covertly hinted earlier are wholly theory-based and un-utilitarian.

For instance, when students are taught what an abstract noun is and, consequently, they are able to argue that 'intelligence' in 'The intelligence of the young man endears him to many' is an abstract noun, what communicative essence does that serve? What value purpose is a debate in an English class on whether the number of parts of speech is eight (8) or more? What functional significance is an extensive discussion on the verb 'is' in an English class, dwelling predominantly on when it is a linking verb (in the main verb capacity) and when it is functioning as an auxiliary verb, as illustrated in 'Africa *is* a blessed continent' and

‘Africa *is* making progress, economically.’, respectively? Again, a student’s proficiency in identifying types of sentence particularly being able to beat the assessment trick seen in phony syntactic extension of the simple sentence and syntactic truncation for the complex sentence, is no pedagogical accomplishment. To this extent, the simple sentence is made longer than the complex sentence as seen in ‘The brilliant young Nigerian dramatist made significant professional impact at the just-concluded World Arts Festival in serene Oswego because of his immense precocity’, and ‘John did well when he was president’. These are a simple sentence and a complex sentence, respectively. This skill is of no value in social communication – inter-personal or group.

In the same vein, being able to assert that ‘there are different types of phrase which are classified based on the headword of the phrase’ (Ekpe 2014: 59) does not guarantee a speaker’s skill in appropriate use of language in fulfilling the social essence of language. Nor is it the appropriate skill to acquire, being able to know that a clause must contain a finite verb which is limited and controlled by the subject that precedes it in terms of person, tense and number (Osisanwo 2014). Or if one knows that a clause contains a finite verb and so does a sentence and that the difference, which distinguishes them, is in meaning conveyance, how does that, in itself find relevance in thought expression and intelligibility – communal or global? It is even the opportune juncture to make an enquiry into what communicative significance it is when an individual is trained to know that ‘that the times are hard’ in ‘The president knows that the times are hard’ is a noun clause, and that it is the object of the transitive verb ‘knows’.

When the students of English studies are expected to devote tremendous time to studying the word arrangement in an active-voice construction, what is the social use of such in academic language enquiries? The current course contents require that students need to know that the determiner(s) come(s) first before a noun if the noun is not a proper noun. Following the noun/pronoun is the verb and the verb must be transitive, so that it can select an object, which is the next syntactic element in the active-voice sentence before the adjunct. This arrangement would produce the code SVOA, standing for Subject-Verb-Object-Adjunct if the same student is trained to pay much attention to origin of words (etymology) and if the same student needs to study extensively on historical (diachronic) assessment of the English language. If the same student must study the social typologies of English, if the same student has got to learn allophones, phonemes and the nitty-gritty of the minimal pair which compels them to master the similarity and difference between, for example, *kiss* and *piss*; and how does this skill improve the speech proficiency of the student? In minimal measures, I dare assert, and this assertion is attributed to the abstract, structural or syntactic nature of these areas of linguistic studies. For this reason, the study of them is merely academic and just for itself or at the maximum, can only be a pre-requisite for a more productive sphere of English.

If it is examined critically, it would be seen that Noam Chomsky stretches and as such rubbishes syntax which is ‘... a systematic statement of rules governing the grammatical arrangement of words and morphemes in a language’ (Adebileje 2013: 9) with his grammaticality and acceptability enunciations, in which case ‘grammatical’ is ‘syntactic’. By this token, an expression which is grammatical (syntactic) may not be acceptable, that is, intelligible. This means, the syntactic may not correspond to intelligibility. This theorization finds palpability in such an instance as ‘The aero plane plants cocoa by the roadside’. This expression complies with syntactic (structural) rules: a balanced concord between the singular subject ‘The aero plane’ which selects the singular verb ‘plants’, and since ‘plants’ (the predicate) is a transitive verb, it permits a nominal element after it as object. ‘Cocoa’ is a noun and it is used after the transitive verb. To complete the clause-structure element order, the adjunct follows the object. However, the unintelligibility palpable in the sentence nullifies the relevance of syntactic grammar. It is therefore, for its own sake, rather theoretical, merely academic!

The unacceptability of the syntactic grammar (in a sphere) in social communication because of relevance or significance of meaning in conversations has accounted for honing of diction and polishing of syntax by the African writer (Osundare 2007) all of which is targeted at nourishing his art on the culture of ‘art for art’s sake’ (22). Critical attention needs to be paid to certain words in the Osundare’s view as above. Such words include ‘honing’, ‘polishing’ and ‘nourishing’. In the context of their semantic signification in the expression, it is seen that all of the words point in the direction of effecting appreciation impact on the hearer/listener/audience. The audience (hearer/listener) is appealed to through appropriate language use such that they understand what is said and the manner of saying it makes language an instrument of conversational social attraction. It can be maintained that this lexical trilogy (hone, polish and nourish) signify artistic communication which is capable of liberating the hearer (Osundare 2008). That is, when writing or speaking is beautified, the reader or listener is persuaded and, consequently, feels adequacy of communication. This is the domain of aesthetics.

Aesthetics can be explained as the concern for the systematic examination of beauty in any object (Abrams 2006: 3). Here, the crux of Abrams’ position is the impact of the phenomenon in focus. In the context of language, beauty is the functionality of its essence – the appreciation of its use on the listener. In that case, language reaches its optimal significance if it performs the function of making the users achieve communication goals. Beauty of language and its functionalities (aesthetics) can be achieved in language use – verbal or graphological – in a number of ways. Each goes a divergent way in the immediate but all converge in the ultimate, and effect a situation of linguistic utilitarianism.

The first is the correctness of English language expressions. This can be seen as grammaticality, not in the context of Chomsky’s syntactic grammaticality but in the context of grammar as ‘... what native speakers of a language possess in their minds that enables

them not only to use their language grammatically, but also to recognise when others are using it grammatically and when they aren't' (Depraetere and Lanaford 2012: 1). The definition finds concrete manifestation in the situation when, rather than pay attention to the definition of syntactic terms or etymological concepts, language academics in non-native colleges pay attention to correctness of English expressions as guided by standard dictionaries such as *Collins English Dictionary*, *Oxford Advanced Learner's Dictionary* or *American Heritage Dictionary*. Here, the quota recommendation we made earlier becomes relevant. That is, if a non-native instructor wants to teach correctness through prepositional collocation, only 20 percent of explanation needs be theoretical – definition(s), etymology, structure et cetera; while the 80 percent remainder should be devoted to the utilitarian significance of the concept, prepositional collocation, being examined. Such utilitarian dimension is the stylistic or phonoaesthetic qualities and purpose of the structural term – all of which are aptly codified as aesthetics. For example, when an academic instructor is discussing the preposition, it is unproductive to devote a significant part of the hour telling the students that a preposition is '... a word used to explain the relationship between two grammatical words or a word used with a noun or a pronoun to show their relationship with some other words in the sentence'. (Murthy 2007: 7). In the same vein, it is not adequate to cite such words as 'on', 'in', 'at', 'for', 'with', 'from', 'behind', 'beneath', and so on as prepositions. These are mere theoretical issues, which are rich resources and substances for memorisation.

The complexity of the English language in the process of attaining grammatical correctness by non-natives is substantial. Such a situation is made worse by the circumstance that the language is not the original language of the Orientals (though it has been localised) making learner-speakers of it having to contend with the consequences of the interference of mother tongues in their attempt to speak the language. Teaching the English preposition arising from this complexity, there is therefore, a scenario of aggravation of the linguistic complexity. This time around, such complexity is occasioned by the inconsistency in the pattern of collocations of the English language. That is, a given verb does select a preposition least-imagined; yet students have been taught preposition and can define it, and can even mention many of the English prepositions.

Such inconsistency in prepositional selection manifests in the verb 'converge', selecting the preposition 'on' in such expressions as 'thousands of supporters *converged on* London for the rally' (*Oxford Advanced Learner's Dictionary (7th Edition)*), 'everyone *converged on* the wounded sailor', 'the shoppers *converged on* the store as it opened for the big sale'. (*The Free Dictionary*. idioms.thefreedictionary.com/converge). Unless having been taught or having experienced it in the native speakers' milieu, such expressions bearing 'converge on' as above are naturally considered anomalous, hence, ungrammatical by the non-native speakers of English. Yet, such speakers are educated and can define a preposition and give examples such as 'on' and 'at'. The insufficiency of the

speech/grammatical proficiency of the non-native speaker as described here above is occasioned by the whole concentration of lectures on preposition, for example, on the structural area of the concept, whereas, there is still the operational (aesthetic) dimension to it all. This should receive 80 percent of the lecture time-space. This would enable the instructor make such clarifications as that there is ‘converge upon’ too in English in this instance, but that this is the formal form which is not as colloquial as ‘converge on’ which is appropriate for everyday conversation. There are many of such words in English, such that not even a four-year degree programme would be enough to exhaust them.

From the perspective of the phrase, the clause and the sentence, it is worthy to aver that directing the objective of linguistic instruction towards the ability of learners to define and identify a phrase in a sentence or in isolation is inadequate. So, investing intellectual energy in enquiries as to the nature of headedness in a phrase is defective as multi-level definitions have made headedness elusive because it is abstract and significantly academic (Keizer 2007). Same applies to the clause and the sentence, too. Ever since I got to know that the words in a group (phrase) are arranged in a natural lineal order and that a phrase does not include subject-predicate affinity, such as ‘The international conference on linguistic aesthetics’, I have not had cause to use the skill in the larger society as a means of communication or in the process of communicating. I have used the knowledge only in the lecture room and this is because I am an academic. Even at that such knowledge in English is not a means of communication, rather, it is the issues that are discussed in the classroom. Therefore, of what communicative essence is it if I expend the significant portion of the time available emphasising that both the clause and the sentence share the similarity of subject-predicate content? And that the difference between the two is in the completeness or otherwise of these syntactic structures. Why should an instructor devote all their time dichotomising the sentence, identifying one as simple and the other complex? If the ultimate essence of a sentence (whether simple, compound, complex or compound complex) is meaning conveyance, does it then matter whether it is simple or complex? All sentence types, irrespective of their structural elements and contents, are the same – they disseminate information and thoughts.

If the sentence ‘I went to United States of America because of money’ is a simple sentence and ‘I went to the United states of America because I wanted money’ is a complex sentence, are not both intelligible if intelligibility is all about comprehension and apprehension of intention through words and phrases? (Nelson 2011:32)? Of course both are and they express the same thought, irrespective of the finiteness of the verb in one and the absence of same in the other. To this end, unbridled elaboration on structure in teaching English/a language is a disdain for purpose, particularly that intelligibility is established or enhanced in a conversational scenario through a natural default in humans. To this end, one does not need the knowledge of the structure or details of the evolutionary or etymological processes of a language to be able to speak the language grammatically,

correctly or acceptably. Folks who do not know the definitions of words or phrase – better still, who are not educated at all speak their languages, excellently in the Orient. As the case is with these folks, so is it with the natives of Liverpool, Leicester or Sussex: and so is it with them in Albany, Baltimore or Albuquerque. They do not necessarily know the syntactic details of the English language, yet they determine the grammaticality of the English language. Syntactic grammar theories are the theoretical enunciations and intellectual commodities of the academics from London, oxford, Cambridge, Harvard and promoted in Ibadan.

Which precedes the other – aesthetics theories or those of syntax/structure of the sentence? The answer to this poser further emphasises the significance and supremacy of the aesthetic perspective to language investigation over its structure. That is, theories of aesthetics preceded syntactic theories. It is because language has been performing functions in society that its structure has been deemed veritable to be theorised. It was only recently that the United Kingdom Universities pioneered the study of English at the collegiate level (Goddard 2012). Socrates, Plato, Aristotle, Cicero, Longinus and many of the classical personalities were masters of aesthetic language use. The evolution of the term *Socratic irony* as an instrument of persuasive language deployment speaks volumes for the inception of aesthetics before syntactic theories or structural enunciations. This could be traced essentially to such masterpieces as Noam Chomsky's *Aspect of the Theory of Syntax* (1965) whose central concern was the syntax of the natural language; and M.A.K. Halliday's *Context and Text*. Obviously these structural investigations as recorded in these books are recent developments. As a result of this, there is tremendous importance that needs be attached to aesthetics. It is, therefore, inadequate to give pedagogical instructions on the English language based significantly on its structure without attention to its functionalities, especially the comprehension and regaling the listener gets in the process of conversing. This is in line with the submission that there is 'the arts of talk' or 'a poetry of talk' (Pope 2012:33) in human conversation or use of language. 'Art' and 'poetry' are synonymous with aesthetics.

One still wonders why consonants and their sounds, their places and manners of articulation and chart representations of the sounds, and so on, still take dominant emphasis in the phonetic class in non-native universities. These, indubitably, are theoretical enunciations which are good to learn and know though, but which have restricted use. The native speakers acquire the skill and proficiencies of speech naturally, as such, do not know (actually do not care about) /b/ as bilabial plosive or /ei/ as a diphthong. Why then is excessive time spent on these concepts in the classroom or on the structure of the English syllable? Speakers do not need to know what a syllable is in order to speak purposively in social conversations. They are conscious of this by default. If the knowledge of the syllable is not mandatory in the bid to speak well in the day-to-day conversation, how then is the knowledge of the structure important such that linguistic terms dominate the curriculum

contents of English studies in the universities in most part of the Orient? Learners of English at the higher level have ever been subjected to learning the structural elements of the English syllable such as onset and rhyme. The rhyme splits into nucleus and coda, such that the 'onset' is the consonant(s), the nucleus is the vowel while the coda is also a consonant. However, this knowledge does not reflect in actual every day communication in English.

Because of the non-significance of these phonological concepts in the articulation of English sounds, minimal amount of time should be expended on them while substantial amount of time is devoted to impact-sensitive topics such as phonaesthetics during teaching. The importance of phonaesthetics in the study of phonetics or phonology is emphasised in the definition of the term as 'the study of the positive (euphonious) and negative (cacophonous) sounds of letters, words, and combination of letters and words' (Nordquist 2017:1). To this end, the investigation of phonaesthetics is the functional properties of sounds that are studied. Such instance is noted in the consideration of sounds, especially plosives, which according to Nordquist, actors pay attention to in choosing their pseudonyms. This, the linguist explains, has led many actors change their names. This could be taught as the implicational essence of plosives. Therefore, rather than spend the whole time discussing the theoretical aspect of 'plosives', extension should be made to what plosives are used for in society. This is in the realm of phonaesthetics; it is result-based; and it is beyond the theoretical. Memorising the plosives is not productive.

Similarly, attention needs be directed to the collation of words with peculiar articulatory processes. Such words need be dissected with the aid use of the dictionary so as to make the investigations empirical. Since the English language is acquired by most speakers in Africa and the rest of the Orient, there is naturally the interference of the mother tongue in an attempt to articulate English words; just as there is orthographic inconsistencies in English word pronunciation by non-native speakers (Egbokhare 2007). As a result of this, there is high proclivity that the 'b' in 'tomb' would be articulated, just as the 'ment' in 'denouement' would be realised as /mɔ̃nt/. In the same vein the 'a' in 'village' has the huge potential to be realised and articulated as the diphthong /ei/ by a non-native speaker. Whereas, the bilabial plosive /b/ is left out in 'tomb', the 'ment' in 'denouement' is realised as /mD/ and the 'a' in 'village' is represented as /i/. There are numerous words with such phonological peculiarities. The number is so high that tremendous time would be needed to discuss them. Therefore, after the theoretical discussions on the consonants and vowels, (which should be minimal), such theoretical discussions should, however, be extended to its application in order to put its manifestations in words to practice. Focus here is not on the regular phonetic realisations, but on the strange phonological situation to the non-native speakers.

The enunciations on the phrase and clause as elements of English syntactic structure should be made thorough but only to the 20 percent of the lecture time and topic contents.

Their significance, that is, how they convey the speaker's thought appropriately needs be emphasised. This can be realised in the form of discussing the left-branch sentences. That is discussing the impact of having a phrase or a clause at the beginning of a sentence rather than at the end of the sentence. Or it could be in the form of investigating which thought unit of the whole thought content(s) of a sentence is contained in the phrase or clause and what the effect of that is in the conveyance of thought from the speaker to the hearer. The manner in which the hearer receives such is also of concern. This applies to the sentence too. After minimal time and energy has been expended on the definitions and typologies of the sentence, this structural knowledge is now extended to why a speaker has chosen to convey a thought through the simple sentence or in a consecutive multiple simple sentences, for example. It could as well be the topic sentence, which is the sentence in the paragraph which 'conveys the central or controlling ideas of each paragraph' (Arayela, 2009: 12). One may discuss the way a speaker makes a peculiar point in the location of the topic sentence in a paragraph. If it comes at the beginning of a paragraph, what point is the writer making? If it is in the middle or the end, why is it so? This is empirical; it is result-bound, it is productive, it is functional – it is aesthetic.

Semantics is taught beyond its definition and variability in terms of lexical relations. Peculiar attention (energy) in this sense is paid to how learners overcome the natural confusion (and the accompanying frustration) emanating from, for example, homophony. There are many homophones in English. The number is so immense that expending much time on definition may be (certainly, is) perfunctory. The necessity of going beyond the theory on semantics finds relevance in the learners' competence in word usage, which is semantic correctness. Such competence enables them use the appropriate words in the appropriate situations to convey thoughts to the hearer appropriately. Building such a skill in university students is unquestionably more result-oriented than concentrating on the definition of semantics. Current situations such that university students (a significant number, really) are not skilled in using the alternative words to institute variety in word usage is a failure of semantic instructions at the collegiate level, especially. Semantic varieties are functional in speech; they are resources of aesthetics. This is attainable if semantics is made empirical and functional rather than being abstract and structural (academic) essentially. This is made complete when denotation, connotation as well as pejoration are emphasised peculiarly under semantic analysis in relation to specific words in large numbers. After all, different meanings are ascribed to words in English (Ezenwanebe 2007) and it is context that signifies the different layers of meaning. The many more words that are examined in the process the better for aesthetic proficiency to be attained.

Conclusion

Though theoretical structural grammar is a necessity in collegiate English studies, but it should be in a certain measure for different categories of people. It is necessary in a tremendous measure for English language academics as it forms the substances of classroom lectures (it is made so in the non-native part of the world). Also, it lends and affords the instructor the professional terms/register with which lectures are delivered as an expert. It is, however, necessary only in a minimal measure for non-academics. It is not all who have received tuition on English that would be academics. Therefore, the knowledge that would be acquired by the non-academic trainee within the 20 percent scope is adequate for what they need theoretical English for. The rest is essentially aesthetic language use in socio-cultural situations.

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